

E3.1 Assessment of DLT Frameworks v1.0

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[6GENABLERS-DLT]
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**6G Networks Enabled through
Technology Driven Solutions
[6GENABLERS]**

**Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
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List of Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DID	Decentralized Identifiers
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
IBFT	Istanbul Byzantine Fault Tolerance
ID	Identifier
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
PoET	Proof of Elapsed Time
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAFT	Reliable, Replicated, Redundant and Fault Tolerant
RBFT	Redundant Byzantine Fault Tolerance
SC	Smart Contract
SCSC	Smart Contract State Composer
SLA	Service Level Agreement
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VM	Virtual Machine
VPN	Virtual Private Network

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable E3.1 Assessment of DLT Frameworks, envisaged in the framework of the project 6GENABLERS-DLT (TSI-063000-2021-12). Starting the technical work of P3, this deliverable provides a comprehensive design of the implementation of the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) system building the distributed marketplace of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, focusing on multi-party transactions in dynamic 6G environments. It presents the study done to select an appropriate DLT solution and the design of the building blocks for the DLT system as part of the Smart Marketplace to be developed within the project. The document describes the guidelines to implement the solution. It describes the components, their provided interfaces, the data models employed and their workflows specifying the pre-conditions, communications phases, dependencies and interactions with other components. Overall, this document serves as a comprehensive guide to implement and integrate the software components of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, paving the way for the development of innovative solutions in the 6G ecosystem.

1 Introduction

1.1 Document Scope and Objectives

The present document stresses on the main technology that sustains the development of a distributed marketplace of 6G networks. The Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) is the base to record any activity on the marketplace and to provide awareness to all participants. On top of that DLT technology different interfaces brokering the reading and writing of agreements and SLA status across providers and clients are specified according to their architecture, interfaces, data model and workflows. Additionally, the distributed ID manager and the interconnectivity mechanism of distributed storage and identifier components across different network domains are also detailed spanning the same corners, architecture, interfaces, data model and workflow. As such, this deliverable provides the definition of the DLT system as a core block to build the 6GENABLERS Marketplace as an enabling technology for future 6G networks.

In correspondence with the aforementioned scope, the primary objectives of this document are as follows:

1. DLT technology selection: The document provides a detailed description of the selected DLT solution, which serves as a crucial core system to enable the capabilities and uses of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. The technology has been selected from analysing 3 alternatives including objective (performance) tests and qualitative factors to ensure that the employed technology is valid for the persistence of transactions of a marketplace of network, computing, and service assets, versatile for different information and users.
2. Internal architecture: The document further presents the component-based architecture including the distributed storage, identity, APIs and connectivity setup. These building blocks contribute to the successful implementation and operation of the multi-party real-time network infrastructure resource trading.
3. Interfaces and data model: In addition to the DLT system architecture, the document details the associated functions provided by the internal components, including the data parameters and formats and the message structures. By specifying the functional details, the document ensures that the DLT system components provide all the information about the provided features, how to use them, the required inputs and the obtained outputs.
4. Workflow diagrams: Lastly, once the individual components and their features are defined, the expected use, the dependencies and the order to chain different functions around different groups of purposes or uses are defined.

1.2 Relation to the Project's Activities

This deliverable constitutes a key outcome of Work Package 3 (P3 - Distributed Ledger Technologies for a Decentralised Marketplace). This work package focuses on the study and evaluation of suitable DLTs identifying the specific DLT solution that will be employed for the implementation of the Marketplace. Then, P3 also put emphasis on components interacting with the DLT system as an enabling technology for multi-party resource and service trading. P3 aims to provide a comprehensive design of the DLT system as enabler of the envisioned DLT-anchored Marketplace platform, detailing the

interfaces employed, the format of the data to be exchanged and the sequence of operations triggered from the different components. The ultimate goal is to document the development and guide the integration of the components of the DLT system, leveraging the capabilities of DLT as a foundational technology.

Figure 1-1 E3.1 positioning and relation to the project's activities

As depicted in Figure 1-1, deliverable E3.1 is the joint result of the work done in 2 tasks within P3, which are listed below:

- A3.1 – DLT Frameworks Analysis: This task focuses on the study and evaluation of suitable DLT solutions as an underlying component of the market. The analysis takes into account qualitative factors, as well as the quantitative evaluation of performance and scalability among the identified candidates. The result of this task provides a technology supporting the building of interoperable and distributed trading systems as input for the design and implementation of the platform.
- A3.2 – Multi-site DLT Testbed enablement: This task implements a multi-site DLT network including the provision of necessary inter-domain connectivity. The use of automation tools is expected to support the deployment. The result of this work aims to provide the DLT infrastructure that emulates a multi-party network of actors in the market.

The requirements gathered from the P2's tasks regarding the system requirements of the technological pillars, written in E2.1, have played a crucial role in shaping the functional architecture of the DLT-anchored Distributed Telco Marketplace. This document is the main input to specify system components and functions implemented in P3, P4, and P5 by means of prototypes. After each developed version, the resulting implementation will be validated checking the platform capabilities to serve assets for multi-party real-time holographic communications services in a later phase during P6's timeframe to check the successful implementation of the envisioned Marketplace.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The current document is structured in several sections that set the stage for defining the components of the DLT system. In particular, the document is structured as follows:

- Section 1: This section provides an overview of the document, including its objectives, the relationship to the project's activities, and the structure of the document itself.
- Section 2: This section presents the results on the analysis and tests done for three DLT frameworks including quantitative evaluation of performance and qualitative features concluding with the selected technology to create a DLT-based Marketplace of 6G networks.
- Section 3: This section presents the internal component-based architecture, implementation design, data models to comply along the interfaces and the planned sequence of operations and responsibilities of each component when performing the different allowed functions. Accordingly, those technical aspects are detailed for the deployment of the Identity Manager API system, Offer API, Order API, and SC-State API components.
- Section 4: The conclusion section summarises the main findings and highlights the key takeaways from the document.
- Section 5: This section lists the sources and references cited throughout the document, providing a comprehensive list of the materials used to support the information presented.

2 Overview of DLT as Enabling Technology

2.1 Considered State-of-the-art DLT Frameworks

This section describes the three DLT networks we have considered in order to compare them and select the best one in terms of best performance. Considering the deliverable D2.1, the selected DLT has to fulfil these criteria:

- 1. Decentralized architecture:** The 6GENABLERS Marketplace needs to be a decentralized architecture by consisting of multiple interconnected platform instances.
- 2. Permissioned environments:** Permissioned DLTs are also known as private DLTs. These DLTs are operated by a single entity or a consortium of entities, and access to the DLT is restricted to a specific group of participants. In this kind of DLTs, the access to the ledger is controlled by a central authority, which verifies and validates all transactions. On the other hand, permissionless DLTs, are also known as public DLTs. They are open to everyone who wants to participate in the network. In this kind of DLTs, there is no central authority that controls access to the network. Instead, users on the network are responsible for verifying and validating transactions. The 6GENABLERS Marketplace is conceived to operate in a permissioned environment, so permissionless DLTs are directly discarded for the analysis.
- 3. Automated governance:** The use of Smart Contracts helps and facilitates the automation and enforcement of SLA rules in the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, as well as avoiding manual interactions having an automated system.
- 4. Transparency and Trust:** As 6GENABLERS Marketplace needs to be transparent, the immutable and transparent nature of the ledger ensures that all transactions and interactions within the Marketplace are recorder and can be audited. The offers information must be transmitted equally to all the nodes of the DLT network. A decentralized network ensures that the information is distributed in all nodes of the DLT network and difficult to manipulate the data inside of it.
- 5. Privacy and Confidentiality:** The transactions performed in the DLT network are to be shared among all network participants. Only network participants need to know the information of transactions.

Considering these capabilities, the considered DLT networks in order to analyse each other are the Hyperledger Fabric, Quorum and Corda, as they fulfil all the above capabilities. Moreover, in order to manages all the identities of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace, the best DLT for that task is the Hyperledger Indy.

2.1.1 Hyperledger Fabric

Hyperledger Fabric [1] is an enterprise-grade, distributed ledger platform that offers modularity and versatility for a broad set of industry use cases. The modular architecture for Hyperledger Fabric accommodates the diversity of enterprise use cases through plug and play components, such as consensus, privacy, and membership services. One of the many compelling Fabric features is the enablement of a network of networks.

Members of a network work together, but because businesses need some of their data to remain private, they often maintain separate relationships within their networks.

Rather than an open, permission-less system, Fabric offers a scalable and secure platform that supports private transactions and confidential contracts. This architecture allows for solutions developed with Fabric to be adapted for any industry, thus ushering in a new era of trust, transparency, and accountability for businesses.

At first, Hyperledger Fabric was designed for enterprise use. It is intended as a foundation for developing applications or solutions with a modular architecture. Its modular and versatile design satisfies a broad range of industry use cases. It offers a unique approach to consensus that enables performance at scale while preserving privacy.

Unlike some other distributed ledger technologies that were originally designed for ad hoc, public use, which had to be significantly redesigned to add in support for permissions and privacy; Hyperledger Fabric was designed with these features as foundational. In this regard, Hyperledger Fabric has had a head start over many of the competing frameworks.

It is shown in the Figure 2-1, the architecture of the Hyperledger Fabric DLT network. As it can be seen it has an orderer node connected to the two organizations that are part of the DLT network as a DLT nodes. This orderer node is responsible for ordering transactions and managing the transactions between the different organizations of the DLT network. The Smart Contracts are referred to as Chaincodes in Hyperledger Fabric containing all the logic of the transaction execution.

Figure 2-1 Hyperledger Fabric DLT architecture

2.1.2 Quorum

The Quorum [2] network is based on a fork of Ethereum [3] blockchain. It is a permissioned or private DLT. Its main purpose is to provide a permissioned implementation of the Ethereum Blockchain that supports contract privacy and transactions.

The highlight of this network is its feature called “private transaction identifier” that ensures data privacy. The primary objective of building Quorum is to utilize the existing technology as much as possible.

The introduction of the Quorum blockchain helped in overcoming this issue as it included new features such as cryptographic protocols, zero-knowledge proofs, homomorphic encryption, etc. Quorum is keeping the essence of Ethereum and utilizing the simple approach to privacy to satisfy the users.

The Figure 2-2, details the architecture [4] of the Quorum DLT, in which the main blocks of the Quorum DLT are shown. The *Transaction Manager* manages access to encrypted transaction data in Quorum as well as managing the platform’s interactions with other transaction managers and the local data store of a Quorum node. The *Crypto Enclave* is responsible for key management and data encryption and decryption in Quorum. The *Consensus* component provides for the use of various consensus mechanisms in Quorum. The *Network Manager* controls access to a Quorum network, thereby enabling a permissioned network of nodes to be created for a Quorum implementation.

Figure 2-2 Quorum DLT architecture

2.1.3 Corda

Corda [5] is a permissioned blockchain as it shares data only with the parties involved in the transaction. Each entity must be tied to a legal entity and granted access to join the network.

This platform, developed by R3, employs a point-to-point data broadcast system. Such a design eliminates the notion of a single principal ledger, opting instead for transactional data to be shared only with those entities on the network specifically involved in the transaction.

Corda binds all on chain contracts to a traditionally recognized written legal agreement outlining the intended use of each contract by allowing for an object to be included in the code. This helps to circumvent the current grey area surrounding the legal enforceability of smart contracts. Furthermore, as a permissioned network, each node must be certified

and linked to a registered entity (the notary node) providing a further layer of legal accountability. The Corda DLT architecture presented in Figure 2-3, is made up of five key layers. The Persistence layer is responsible for data storage in Corda. The *Network* interface layer is responsible for interaction between a Corda node and other nodes in Corda Network. The *RPC Client* allows a Corda node owner to interact with the node under its ownership through RPC calls. The *ServiceHub* provides capabilities that allow a given Corda node to call its other services. Finally, CorDapp layer allows a given Corda node to be extended through the installation of CorDapps.

Figure 2-3 Corda DLT architecture

2.1.4 Hyperledger Indy

Hyperledger Indy [6] is a blockchain framework that is specifically designed for decentralized identity management. It offers solutions for individuals and organizations to secure and manage digital identities, ensuring privacy and security.

Hyperledger Indy is built on the principles of decentralized identity. Instead of relying on a central authority or identity provider, individuals create and control their own digital identities. These identities are stored on the blockchain (ledger), ensuring their authenticity and security. To do so, Indy uses Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) to identify individuals and entities on the network. Verifiable credentials, which are cryptographically signed attestations, allow users to share their personal information with others in a secure and privacy-preserving manner.

This framework was chosen to promote the credentials management of the DLT framework, this was due after analysing its principles of working and pointing out its main advantages, which includes:

1. **Privacy:** The decentralized nature of Hyperledger Indy, coupled with zero-knowledge proofs, ensures that users can share only the necessary information with trusted parties.
2. **Security:** Digital identities stored on the blockchain are highly secure and tamper-resistant.
3. **Interoperability:** Hyperledger Indy can be integrated with other Hyperledger frameworks, such as Hyperledger Fabric and external systems.
4. **Reduced Reliance on Central Authorities:** Actors are no longer dependent on centralized identity providers, reducing the risk of data breaches and privacy violations.
5. **User Control:** Self-sovereign identity empowers users to control their personal data, decide who can access it, and easily revoke access when needed.

2.2 Criteria for Assessment and Analysis of Tests

This section describes all the criteria imposed to test and compare the three short-listed DLTs. We have differentiated into three different primary parameters groups: information, feature, and performance parameters. The parameters we have considered to compare the DLTs are the following:

1. Information parameters:

- **Type:** Type of DLT between permissioned or permissionless. Our analysis is based on permissioned DLTs as a requirement of 6GENABLERS Marketplace.
- **Version:** Version of the DLT network deployment.
- **License:** License type between DLTs. They can be Open Source, accessible for all users; or Enterprise, only accessible for subscriber users.
- **Persistence type:** Type of DLT. They can be Blockchain, Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG), Hashgraph, Holochain, Tempo, etc.
- **Documentation:** Ease of documentation when deploying, configuring, reading, etc.

2. Feature parameters:

- **Deployment mode:** Type of deployment modes. The DLTs deployments are divided into two different modes: single and multi-host.

Figure 2-4 Single and multi-host modes in DLT deployment

The Figure 2-4 shows the two different deployment modes of the DLT. In the single-node mode, all the DLT nodes are placed in the same virtual machine, and they communicate each other by the consensus algorithm. However, in the multi-node mode, each DLT node is placed in a different virtual machine. In this case, to communicate each other, they must share the same network. To have a distributed system, the best way to deploy our DLT network is to deploy it in a multi-host mode, that is each DLT node is a different virtual machine.

- **Programming language:** The programming language accepted and used by the DLT.
- **Consensus algorithm:** Consensus algorithm used by the DLT.
- **Privacy:** Possibility of the DLT network for performing private and public transactions.
- **Modularity:** Degree to which a system's components may be separated and recombined.
- **Computing resources:** The minimum computing resources per DLT node needed for the deployment of the DLT network.

3. Performance parameters:

- **DLT deployed nodes:** Deployed DLT nodes for the analysis.
- **CPU Usage in the DLT deployment:** The percentage of CPU usage when the DLT is deployed.
- **Nodes scalability:** The facility of scaling up the nodes in the network.
- **Nodes stability:** The stability of the DLT nodes once the network is deployed and transactions are performed.
- **Time of deployment:** The time of deployment in seconds while de DLT network is deploying in single-host mode.
- **Average Tx latency:** Average latency between transactions performed by the DLT network. The transactions are sent in two different modes: series and parallel. On the one hand, when the transactions are sent in series, they are sent one by one in the DLT, waiting for the confirmation of the DLT that the transaction is complete. On the other hand, when the transactions are sent in parallel, they are sent simultaneously. To measure the latency, we have designed a stress test for each DLT performing transactions both in series and in parallel.
- **Average Tx CPU usage:** The percentage of the CPU used when transactions both in series and in parallel are performed in the DLT network.

2.3 Conclusion Derived from Assessed Frameworks

After performing the corresponding tests to analyse the performance of each of the DLTs, the results obtained are summarized in Figure 2-5 and in Table 2-1.

Figure 2-5 Comparison of CPU usage when DLT is deployed.

As a first result, in Figure 2-5, it can be seen the comparison of the CPU usage when the DLTs are deployed. For this analysis, the deployment was in single-host mode and each DLT network contains 3 DLT nodes. It is clearly shown that Corda is the one that consumes the most CPU usage getting closer to 100% of the CPU. However, Hyperledger Fabric is the DLT that consumes the least CPU usage in the first 25 seconds when the nodes are setting up.

The Table 2-1 shows all the results after analysing the 3 DLTs with the criteria imposed for the comparison and with the different requirements necessary for the DLT network to be as versatile, efficient, and stable as possible.

Table 2-1 Corda, Quorum and Hyperledger Fabric comparison

	CORDA	QUORUM	HYPERLEDGER FABRIC
INFORMATION			
Type	Permissioned	Permissioned	Permissioned
License	Open Source/Enterprise	Open Source	Open Source
Version	4.10 (Latest)	23.4.0 (Latest)	2.5 (Latest)
Persistence type	DAG	Blockchain	Blockchain
Documentation	Poor understanding	Well understanding	Well understanding
FEATURES			
Deployment mode	Single-host ✓ Multi-host ✗	Single-host ✓ Multi-host ✓	Single-host ✓ Multi-host ✓
Programming language	Java	JavaScript/Solidity	Java/Go/JavaScript
Consensus algorithm	Pluggable/RAFT/IBFT	Pluggable/RAFT/IBFT	Pluggable/PoET/RAFT/Kafka

Privacy	Transactions private by default	Supports private and public transactions	Channels and private data collections permit high customization
Modularity	Medium	Medium	High
Computing Resources	4vCPUs, 8GB RAM, 80GB Disk	4vCPUs, 8GB RAM, 80GB Disk	2vCPUs, 4GB RAM, 40GB Disk
PERFORMANCE			
DLT deployed nodes	3	3	3
Deployment Average CPU Usage	Single-host: 77,046% Multi-host: N/A	Single-host: 38,553% Multi-host: 5,421%	Single-host: 1,906% Multi-host: 5,840%
Deployment time in single-host mode (s)	~ 200	~ 75	~ 25
Nodes scalability	Easy	Easy	Medium
Nodes stability	Poor	Good	Good
Average Tx latency (s)	Single node Series/Parallel		
	7,2077 / 0,2425	235,0081 / 0,1098	85,34 / 0,3377
	Multi node Series/Parallel		
	N/A	688,7764 / 0,5124	68,7056 / 0,4893
Tx CPU Usage (%)	Single-host: 46,464 % Multi-host: N/A	Single-host: 9,1815 % Multi-host: 8,315 %	Single-host: 2,782 % Multi-host: 8,008 %

The results and conclusions after analysing the considered DLTs that are resumed in Table 2-1 are the subsequent:

1. In terms of **information** parameters, we obtain the following:
 - The **type** of all the analysed DLTs is permissioned as it is a requirement of 6GENABLERS Marketplace explained in Section 2.1. This type of DLTs reduce the risks associated with public DLTs, where anyone can join and participate in the consensus process.
 - The three analysed DLTs **license** are open-source and accessible for user utilization. An exception is Corda, which offers an Enterprise version with technical support.
 - The **version** used for the analysis is the latest one in all the considered DLTs.
 - Regarding the **persistence type**, two DLTs of blockchain type have been used (Hyperledger Fabric and Quorum), and one of type DAG (Corda).
 - In terms of the **documentation**, both Hyperledger Fabric and Quorum present a well understood documentation, with some guidelines to getting started with the DLT network. Corda's documentation, however, is not well understood and is confusing, which makes understanding the network and its deployment more complicated.

2. Regarding the **features** parameters of each analysed DLT, we obtain the following:
- Regarding **deployment modes**, the analysis show that Hyperledger Fabric and Quorum were correctly deployed in single and multi-host mode both correctly deployed and fully functional. Finally, it is noted that in Corda was correctly deployed and functional in single-host mode. However, the deployment of Corda in multi-host mode was unable to be achieved. The deployment in a multi-host environment has been tested given the best result and functionality with Hyperledger Fabric DLT network.
 - In terms of **programming languages**, it can be seen that Hyperledger Fabric is more flexible accepting three different programming languages. Quorum is still flexible, but it accepts only two languages. Corda, instead, is not flexible in this criterion, as it only accepts one programming language, which makes it tighter.
 - Analysing the **consensus algorithms**, Hyperledger Fabric relies on Reliable, Replicated, Redundant and Fault Tolerant (RAFT) consensus algorithm for its ordering service. It enables ordering nodes to establish consensus through leader election, log replication and commit procedures. Corda uses a notary-based consensus mechanism, where specialized nodes called notaries validate transactions. Quorum, a fork of Ethereum, supports both Raft-based consensus and Istanbul BFT, a Byzantine Fault Tolerant consensus algorithm.
 - With respect to the **privacy** of the network, Hyperledger Fabric offers various privacy features, such as private data collections and channels, to ensure that sensitive data is protected and only accessible by authorized participants. Corda provides privacy through its point-to-point communication, ensuring that transaction data is only shared with the relevant parties. Quorum, designed for enterprise use, includes privacy features like private transactions and private smart contracts, which ensure that sensitive data remains confidential within a consortium network.
 - Regarding the **modularity** of the DLT network, the modular architecture of Hyperledger Fabric separates the transaction processing workflow in three different stages: smart contracts called chaincode that comprise the distributed logic processing and agreement of the system, transaction ordering and transaction validation.
 - With respect to the minimum **computing resources** required by each node of the DLT to deploy the network, Hyperledger Fabric consumes the least resources compared to Corda and Quorum, making it the most efficient in terms of resources.
3. Regarding the **performance** parameters of each analysed DLT, we obtain the following:
- The **DLT deployed nodes** refers to the deployed nodes used in all the tests. In all of the networks, the number of deployed nodes is 3. All the tests have been performed with the same number of nodes in each DLT.
 - In relation to the **average CPU usage when deployment** of the DLT network is performed is only measured in single-host mode, as the deployment of Corda was unable to be achieved in the multi-host mode.

- In terms of the **time of deployment** in single-host mode, the Hyperledger Fabric is the faster one, in which the nodes are deployed in 25s more or less. Instead, Corda and Quorum, take more time in order to deploy the nodes of the DLT network.
- In relation to the **scalability of the nodes**, i.e. adding one more node to the network, it is observed that in all three DLTs, it is possible to scale the number of nodes, although it is observed that in the case of Hyperledger Fabric the scalability is somewhat more complex with respect to Corda and Quorum. The procedure in order to scale the network to add one node more to it is more confusing in Hyperledger Fabric. To measure this performance parameter, both Corda and Quorum were scaled to 7 nodes without any problems using docker compose. Instead, Hyperledger Fabric, was scaled to 4 nodes and its procedure was more difficult.
- Regarding the **stability of the nodes** once the network has been deployed, it can be observed that both Quorum and Hyperledger Fabric have high network stability, while Corda lost connectivity between nodes and the network was not stable. It was observed that when performing the stress test and stressing the network to perform up to 1000 transactions, both Hyperledger Fabric and Quorum performed the transactions correctly, in contrast, in Corda, the network went offline, unable to successfully perform the transactions, crashed and then went down.
- Analysing **the average latency between transactions**, we have divided in two the results obtained after performing the stress tests in the two different deployment modes, either the deployment of the network in a single node, or the deployment in several nodes. The results show the average latency when 100 assets are sent either in series or in parallel. First, we obtain the results for both serial and parallel transactions in the single-host mode, giving the best results in Corda and followed by Hyperledger Fabric. However, we observe that in the multi-node environment, there has been no deployment of Corda, and the best result with respect to latency is given by Hyperledger Fabric. Therefore, analysing this point, the best and most latency-efficient network is Hyperledger Fabric, allowing deployment in both environments and with better results.
- As a last analysis, we have **the percentage of CPU used in sending transactions**, performing the stress test up to 100 transactions. It is observed that Corda has no results in the multi-node environment, because it has not been able to perform the deployment, and the result obtained with respect to the single node environment is much worse with respect to Quorum and Hyperledger Fabric. Between the latter two, there is a small improvement in terms of CPU consumption in Hyperledger Fabric, so it is concluded that on this point, Hyperledger Fabric is the most efficient.

As a summary, Hyperledger Fabric allows for a wide variety of configurations, meaning it is possible to design a highly decentralized network if chosen to do so. It can be implemented with a multi-node architecture distributed across different organizations, promoting decentralization in terms of control and governance.

Moreover, it offers a highly modular architecture that allows developers to customize and adapt the network to their specific needs. This is especially valuable for enterprise

applications that require flexibility in terms of governance and privacy. While Quorum and Corda are also flexible DLTs, Hyperledger Fabric provides a greater diversity of configuration and consensus options, which can be beneficial in complex enterprise environments.

Hyperledger Fabric offers great flexibility in configuring governance and privacy policies, which is vital in business environments that require detailed control over who can access and manage the network. However, Quorum and Corda, while they also support privacy policies, some implementations may be less versatile in terms of governance.

To summarize and after analyzing all the results obtained, it is concluded that the best and most efficient network according to our needs for the project is Hyperledger Fabric, allowing us to deploy in a multi-node environment and being the one with less consumption and lower latency between transactions. Moreover, since Corda and Quorum have a simple architecture, Hyperledger Fabric is more modular.

Once the Hyperledger Fabric has been selected as the most efficient network, a study has been made to find out which programming language is the optimal one for the implementation. As mentioned before, the Hyperledger Fabric accepts three different programming languages: Java, JavaScript and Go. So, a comparison between them has been made in order to see which programming language is the optimal one as it describes the Table 2-2.

Table 2-2 Hyperledger Fabric programming languages comparison

Programming language	Go	JavaScript	Java
Network nodes	3	3	3
Network deployment	2,3553	2,4050	2,3849
Channel creation	10,1681	10,2283	10,2189
Chaincode creation	57,6873	135,6519	46,5360
1 asset	0,0011	0,0024	0,0059
10 assets	0,0056	0,0122	0,0578
50 assets	0,1527	0,5902	0,7818
100 assets	1,1498	2,3650	3,4014
1000 assets	46,3729	50,6599	52,6830

The table above describes the time it takes for the network to perform deployment, channel and chaincode creation, as well as the time it takes to perform transactions (1,10,50,100 and 1000 assets). It is observed that, in most cases, Go is the programming language that introduces the least latency and is therefore the most efficient, even considering that in the creation of the chaincode it is a little slower than Java in this case. In general, it is the most effective considering the other two programming languages that are accepted by Hyperledger Fabric. So finally, our implementation will be developed in Hyperledger Fabric with Go programming language.

3 DLT System Specification

3.1 Overview

The DLT system is the core network of the 6GENABLERS platform. It enables to have a distributed database in each node of the network allowing to have data saved in the DLT, known by all the nodes that compose the DLT network. This system makes use of an Application Programming Interface (API) to interact with the rest of 6GENABLERS Marketplace. The DLT allows to save, modify, or delete the offers, orders, and smart contract states, which follow up the lifecycle of acquired assets to, for instance, track any occurrence of SLA violations.

3.2 Design Guidelines

The DLT system includes several components that are essential to build the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. It provides the distributed storage needed to persistently record and disseminate transactions across all stakeholders in an immutable manner. The information is transmitted using APIs to store or update new agreements or load existing ones. The information stored are offers of available resources, orders, once negotiated and agreed to provide specific items and configurations and a third one to record the SLA and breaches in the case the provided resources are not satisfying the commitments included in the order. This means that the APIs are passive and waiting for requests from the Marketplace to interact with the distributed storage. As the local or remote provisioning of resources is an action that takes time to a local infrastructure broker, this local broker would need to call the order API with any update on the provisioning status. Thus, any stakeholder would need to poll the order API to get the status information. In a similar manner, any system monitoring SLA conditions and identifying a violation should call the SC-State API. Beyond the interfaces to access the storage, this system provides an identity service to ask for new distributed identities for users and to ask for distributed identities for transactions. Then any request from a user can be verified before it is performed by the APIs into the distributed storage. Furthermore, to ensure that all the distributed storages building the 6GENABLERS marketplace can interconnect through the different infrastructure domains of the users, which have a local instance of the whole DLT system, to which they perform all the requests, a VPN bridge is needed to be deployed, configured and run to ensure the reachability of all the distributed identities and storage systems. To develop these components, a set of comprehensive design guidelines has been formulated.

These guidelines are strategically crafted to facilitate the development, deployment, pipelining of components and utilisation of the information produced in a manner that aligns with both technical excellence and versatile functionality. So, the practices that underpin the successful implementation of the DLT system components are listed below.

- **Modular Architecture:** Develop the DLT system as a modular architecture to ensure scalability, maintainability and interoperability. This facilitates the addition of new functionalities or updates without disrupting the entire system.
- **Separation of Concerns:** Divide the components into well-defined functional entities, each responsible for a specific task (such as Offering, Order and SC-State APIs, the Trading DLT the DID manager and the VPN installer). This

enhances clarity, ease of troubleshooting, independent development, and extensible features.

- **API-driven Structure:** Implement an API-driven structure that allows seamless interaction between the Smart Contract system, the local provisioning brokers and SLA breach detectors and the distributed DLT of the Marketplace framework. Clearly define the input and output formats for each API to ensure smooth integration.
- **Asynchronous Processing:** Provide polling functions to report updated information or status as changes are recorded. These polling functions receive the information and store it for other system components to request the information.
- **Configurability:** Provide configuration options for setting parameters like permitted requests, systems visibility, number of instances, volumes of requests, among others. This allows system administrators to customize the component to suit specific needs.
- **Automated deployment:** Providing scripts to automate deployment of components, configuration of connectivity, and loading of settings including the indexing of local systems.

By adhering to these guidelines, the DLT system components can embody a robust architecture, scalable capabilities, and advanced functionalities, providing a distributed recording of deals and status using provided identifiers. Following these design guidelines ensures that the DLT system is not only technically robust but also flexible enough to process different entities like (offers, orders and SLAs) and satisfy the system's objectives.

3.3 Sub-components

This section describes all the sub-components that compose the DLT system. The architecture in Figure 3-1, details the internal architecture blocks of this main component.

Figure 3-1 DLT system internal architecture

3.3.1 Trading DLT

The Trading DLT is responsible for saving the data related to the orders, offers and SC states. It is a distributed database, so all the DLT nodes have the same information in real time, that is, when a transaction is performed in the DLT network, it is distributed through all the DLT nodes of the network at the same time. It should be noted that factors such as network latency or transaction processing time must be considered when talking about "real time". As we have detailed in Section 2.3, the deployment of the DLT is done by Hyperledger Fabric. This DLT network, features a node called "orderer" that does this transaction ordering. In addition to their ordering node, orderers also maintain the list of organizations of the "orderer system channel". By default, this list, and the channel it lives on, can only be edited by the orderer admin. Orderers [7], also enforce basic access control for channels, restricting who can read and write data to them, and who can configure them. As Hyperledger Fabric's design relies on deterministic consensus algorithms, any block validated by the peer is guaranteed to be final and correct. This called ordering node is the first to be deployed of all the DLT network, then the rest of the nodes are added to the DLT network.

The Figure 3-2 below, describes the Hyperledger Fabric deployment. The deployment has been performed on four different virtual machines. As a first approach, the deployment has been performed in virtual machines because of facility of deployment. Each DLT node has been deployed through Docker in a different Virtual Machine. It is observed that the four virtual machines share the same Docker network through Docker Swarm in order to communicate with each other in this specific setup.

On the other hand, it is also observed that one of the machines has an orderer node deployed. This node acts as the DLT manager, enabling the possibility of carrying out transactions between the nodes. This orderer node is the first to be deployed, so that the other nodes know with whom they must communicate at the time of deployment. The other nodes are the DLT nodes themselves that are part of the network. As can be seen, each node is in a different virtual machine, but they share the same network. The automatization of the DLT deployment will be supported by Kubernetes or by Docker Swarm. This capability will be further elaborated in upcoming deliverables.

Figure 3-2 Hyperledger Fabric Deployment

3.3.2 Identity Manager API

The Identity Manager API module exists to manage identities and identifiers through the whole Identity DLT network. Using Hyperledger Indy, a framework that provides digital identities rooted on distributed ledgers, which is described in section 2.1.4, the module is responsible to issue, validate and revoke identities for stakeholders and for offers and orders. Using the concept of decentralized identifiers (DIDs), the permission module assures each offer is made by the true resource owner, each order placed is done by the respective consumer. In addition to identifying the stakeholders, DIDs will be also generated to identify other entities to be shared cross-domains such as offers, orders and SC states.

3.3.3 Offering API

The Offering API is used for the management of offers in the Trading DLT. This includes retrieving all existing offers, creating a new offer, updating an offer and cancelling an offer in the marketplace. By cancelling an active offer, the status changes to 'cancelled' although the record of the offer remains in the Trading DLT and can still be viewed.

3.3.4 Order API

The Order API is provided to manage the orders in the Trading DLT. This includes retrieving all existing orders in the Marketplace, adding a new order, updating an order and cancelling an active order. By cancelling an active order, the status changes to 'cancelled' although the record of the order remains in the Trading DLT and can still be viewed.

3.3.5 SC-State API

The SC-State API allows for the recording and management of Smart Contract States. This API will be used to trigger the deployment of resources by writing to the Data Bus. The SC-States can be updated to record changes to the status of the SLA compliance. By sending a DELETE request to this API, the status changes to 'cancelled' although the record of the SC-State remains in the Trading DLT and can still be viewed.

3.4 Interfaces and Data Models

In terms of interfaces, all the sub-components of the DLT system are expected to interact with a range of other key components.

3.4.1 Identity Manager API

The endpoints exposed by the Identity API are outlined next, from Table 3-1 to Table 3-8.

Table 3-1 POST Identity endpoint, deploy instance

Operation name: DeployInstance (/instance/deploy)		
Description	Deploy a new instance of Hyperledger Indy for an actor. It accesses an existing pool and generates a wallet, where it is stored the steward parameters.	
Input Parameters	Type	Description

	N/A	N/A	No input, this function initiates a new instance for an actor.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	steward_did steward_verkey	dict	Dict containing the recently created steward did and its verkey. This steward is used then to publish and to get access to the nodes of the Identity DLT.
Notes			
When this function is called, the instance is initiated. It connects to the pool of Hyperledger Indy and creates a wallet, a secure data structure to store the steward's did and verkey. The steward is used to sign transaction when publishing items into the Identity DLT. This function returns the did and the verkey in a dict form.			
Variable name	Type	Value example	
steward_did	str	"Th7MpTaRZVRYnPiabds81Y"	
steward_verkey	str	"F4U8CjAi2bz8dt6W7YzDSyaWvrFHWQuxCT46Bp14Gb3f"	

Table 3-2 POST Identity endpoint, create new instance

Operation name: CreateNewInstance (/instance/new)			
Description		Create a new instance for an actor, generating a did and a verkey for this actor	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	N/A	N/A	No input, this function generates a did and a verkey for the actor the recently created an instance.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	actor_did actor_verkey	dict	Dict containing the did and verkey assigned to the actor that is deploying its new instance
Notes			
This function creates and assign a new did and verkey to an actor. These two values are the return of this function			
Variable name	Type	Value example	
actor_did	str	"SoBJXBaGcgHUP6Kt7Ecxs3"	
actor_verkey	str	"F4U8CjAi2bz8dt6W7YzDSyaWvrFHWQuxCT46Bp14Gb3f"	

Table 3-3 POST Identity endpoint, add instance to ledger

Operation name: AddInstacetoledger (/instance/addtoledger)			
Description		Add a pair of did and verkey to the Identity DLT using the steward key	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	actor_did actor_verkey	dict	Pair of did and verkey of actor recently created.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	transaction_response	dict	Response with information coming from the Identity DLT confirming the transaction.
Notes			
Publish in the Identity DLT the actor recently created during the deployment. It is stored in the ledger the actors did and verkey			
Variable name	Type	Value example	
actor_did	str	"SoBJXBaGcgHUP6Kt7Ecxs3"	

actor_verkey	str	"F4U8CjAi2bz8dt6W7YzDSyaWvrFHWQuxCT46Bp14Gb3f"
transaction_response	dict	Hyperledger Indy dict response

Table 3-4 GET Identity endpoint, retrieve verkey

Operation name: GetVerkey (/instance/verkey/<actor_id>)		
Description		Access the Identity DLT and collect the respective verkey correspondent to the actor's did given.
Input Parameters		Type Description
actor_id	str	Actor did created during instantiation and stored in the Identity DLT
Output Parameters		Type Description
actor_verkey	str	Verkey stored in the Identity DLT
Notes		
This function accesses the Identity DLT and using the did received as input, retrieves the respective verkey associated with this did, the verkey is the return of the function.		
Variable name	Type	Value example
actor_id		"SoBJXBaGcgHUP6Kt7Ecxs3"
actor_verkey		"F4U8CjAi2bz8dt6W7YzDSyaWvrFHWQuxCT46Bp14Gb3f"

Table 3-5 GET Identity endpoint, compare verkey

Operation name: CompareVerkey (/instance/verkey/compare)		
Description		Compare if a given pair of actors did and verkey are the ones that are truly stored in the Identity DLT
Input Parameters		Type Description
actor_id actor_verkey	dict	Actor did and actor verkey created during instantiation and stored in the Identity DLT
Output Parameters		Type Description
match	bool	Boolean if the input values are the ones stored in the Identity DLT
Notes		
This is a function that returns a Boolean comparing the verkey passed as input with the verkey published in the Identity DLT. This function works to verify if a verkey is associated with the actor did.		
Variable name	Type	Value example
actor_id	Str	"SoBJXBaGcgHUP6Kt7Ecxs3"
actor_verkey	Str	"F4U8CjAi2bz8dt6W7YzDSyaWvrFHWQuxCT46Bp14Gb3f"
match	Bool	"True", "False"

Table 3-6 POST Identity endpoint, create item DID

Operation name: CreateItemDID (/item/create)		
Description		Assign a did for an item (offer/order/SC-state) and publish it into the Identity DLT
Input Parameters		Type Description
actor_id actor_verkey	Dict	An id is created for the item, and it is associated with the actors did and verkey. This id is published in the Identity DLT. In the case

item item_assoc		that item is a SC-State, it is also associated with an offer id described by <i>item_assoc</i> .
Output Parameters	Type	Description
transaction_response	Dict	A response from the Identity DLT confirming that the transaction was successfully done.
Notes		
This function creates an identification for an item passed as parameter and stores this identification in the Identity DLT. This identification more than be linked to the offer/order/SC-State, it is also associated with the actor that is putting the offer/order/SC-State.		
Variable name	Type	Value example
actor_id	Str	"SoBJXBaGcgHUP6Kt7Ecxs3"
actor_verkey	Str	"F4U8CjAi2bz8dt6W7YzDSyaWvrFHWQuxCT46Bp14Gb3f"
item	Str	"OFFER", "ORDER", "SCSTATE"
item_assoc	Str	"SoBJXBaGcgHUP6Kt7Ecxs3"
transaction_response	Dict	Hyperledger Indy dict response

Table 3-7 GET Identity endpoint, retrieve item DIDs associated with actor

Operation name: GetItemsDID (/item/get)		
Description	Get list of item dids (offer/order/SC-state) stored in the Identity DLT	
Input Parameters	Type	Description
actor_id actor_verkey item	Dict	The did and the verkey are used to retrieve all orders or offers associated with the respective actor. The input <i>item</i> determines the kind of the item (offer/order/SC-state).
Output Parameters	Type	Description
Item_id	List	List of all item dids associated with the actor
Notes		
This function retrieves and returns the list of all item dids that are already created and published in the Identity DLT of a specific actor.		
Variable name	Type	Value example
actor_id	Str	"SoBJXBaGcgHUP6Kt7Ecxs3"
actor_verkey	Str	"F4U8CjAi2bz8dt6W7YzDSyaWvrFHWQuxCT46Bp14Gb3f"
item	Str	"OFFER", "ORDER", "SCSTATE"
item_id	List	["SoBJXBaGcgHUP6Kt7Ecxs3"]

Table 3-8 DELETE Identity endpoint

Operation name: DeleteWallet (/instance/delete)		
Description	Delete existing wallet	
Input Parameters	Type	Description
N/A	N/A	
Output Parameters	Type	Description

	deletion_confirmation	Bool	A confirmation that the wallet was successfully deleted.
Notes			
N/A			

3.4.2 Offering API

The body of the requests relating to offers is based on the data models in Deliverable E4.1 [8], covering the design of the Smart Contract System that will act as the entry point for interacting with the 6GENABLERS Marketplace. The endpoints exposed by the Offering API are outlined next, from Table 3-9 to Table 3-13.

Table 3-9 POST Offer Endpoint

Operation name: NewOffer (/market/offer)			
Description		Endpoint for creating a new offer in the Trading DLT.	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	Offer Data	Object	The data of the offer to be added to the Trading DLT is passed to the API in the body of the JSON request.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	N/A	N/A	N/A
Notes			
This endpoint is called by the Smart Contract State Composer (SCSC) component. Then, this API needs to call the Smart Discovery API to obtain a Cluster ID before recording the offer info in the Trading DLT. Refer to the Deliverable E4.1 for the Data Models that will be used to create a new offer.			

Table 3-10 PUT Offer Endpoint

Operation name: ChangeOfferStatus (/market/offer/<offer_id>)			
Description		Endpoint for updating the status of an offer.	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	offer_id	string	Identifier (DID) of the offer whose status is to be updated
	Offer Data	Object	The updated data of the offer
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	N/A	N/A	N/A
Notes			
The details of the offer and the updated status are sent in the body of the PUT request as JSON. Refer to the Deliverable E4.1 for the Data Models that will be used to update an existing offer.			

Table 3-11 DELETE Offer Endpoint

Operation name: RemoveOffer (/market/offer/<offer_id>)			
Description		Endpoint for removing an offer from the marketplace.	
Input Parameters		Type	Description

	offer_id	string	Identifier of the offer whose status is to be removed
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	N/A	N/A	N/A
Notes			
N/A			

Table 3-12 GET ALL Offers Endpoint

Operation name: GetAllOffers (/market/offer)			
Description		Endpoint for retrieving all offers in the Trading DLT	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	N/A	N/A	N/A
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	response	JSON	Returns a list all of the offers in the Trading DLT.
Notes			
Refer to the Deliverable E4.1 for the Data Models of the list of offers that will be returned.			

Table 3-13 GET Offers by Cluster Id Endpoint

Operation name: GetAllOffersByClusterId (/market/offer/cluster/<cluster_id>)			
Description		Endpoint for retrieving all offers for a specified cluster in the Trading DLT	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	cluster_id	integer	The ID of the cluster to be used as a filter for the returned offers
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	response	List	Contains all of the offers in the Trading DLT that match the specified cluster_id parameter
Notes			
Refer to the Deliverable E4.1 for the Data Models of the list of offers that will be returned.			

3.4.3 Order API

The endpoints exposed by the Order API are outlined next, from Table 3-14 to Table 3-17.

Table 3-14 POST Order Endpoint

Operation name: CreateOrder (/market/order)			
Description		Endpoint for adding a new order to the Trading DLT.	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	Order Data	Object	The data of the order to be added to the Trading DLT is passed to the API in the body of the JSON request.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	N/A	N/A	N/A
Notes			

The details of the order are sent to the API in the body of the request in JSON format
Refer to the Deliverable E4.1 for the Data Models that will be used to create a new order.

Table 3-15 DELETE Order Endpoint

Operation name: DeleteOrder (/market/order/<order_id>)			
Description	Endpoint for cancelling an active order in the Trading DLT.		
Input Parameters	Type	Description	
order_id	string	The identifier of the order to be cancelled.	
Output Parameters	Type	Description	
N/A	N/A	N/A	
Notes			
N/A			

Table 3-16 PUT Order Endpoint

Operation name: UpdateOrder (/market/order/order_id)			
Description	Endpoint for updating an existing order in the Trading DLT.		
Input Parameters	Type	Description	
order_id	string	The identifier of the order to be updated.	
Order Data	object	The data of the order to be updated is passed to the API in the body of the JSON request.	
Output Parameters	Type	Description	
N/A	N/A	N/A	
Notes			
The details of the order are sent to the API in the body of the request in JSON format Refer to the Deliverable E4.1 for the Data Models that will be used to update an existing order.			

Table 3-17 GET All Orders Endpoint

Operation name: GetAllOrders (/market/order)			
Description	Endpoint for reading all orders in the marketplace.		
Input Parameters	Type	Description	
N/A	N/A	N/A	
Output Parameters	Type	Description	
response	List	Contains all of the orders in the Trading DLT.	
Notes			
Refer to the Deliverable E4.1 for the Data Models of the list of orders that will be returned.			

3.4.4 SC-State API

The endpoints exposed by the SC-State API are outlined next, from Table 3-18 to Table 3-22.

Table 3-18 POST SC-State Endpoint

Operation name: CreateSCState (/market /scstate)			
Description		Endpoint for recording Smart Contract States.	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	request	JSON	The body of the request details the corresponding information about the post-deployment status of acquired assets.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	N/A	N/A	N/A
Notes			
The SC-State data is sent to the API in the body of the request in JSON format. For the Data Models of this request, refer to deliverable E4.1.			

Table 3-19 DELETE SC-State Endpoint

Operation name: CancelSCState (/market /scstate /< scstate_id>)			
Description		Endpoint for cancelling Smart Contract States.	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	scstate	string	The identifier of the Smart Contract State to be cancelled.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	N/A	N/A	N/A
Notes			
N/A			

Table 3-20 PUT SC-State Endpoint

Operation name: UpdateSCState (/market/scstate /<scstate_id>)			
Description		Endpoint for updating a Smart Contract State – this can be used to record a SLA breach.	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	scstate_id	string	The identifier of the Smart Contract State to be updated.
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	N/A	N/A	N/A
Notes			
The SC-State data is sent to the API in the body of the request in JSON format. For the Data Models of this request, refer to deliverable E4.1.			

Table 3-21 GET SC-State Endpoint

Operation name: GetSCState (/market /scstate /<scstate_id>)			
Description		Endpoint for reading a specific Smart Contract State.	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	scstate_id	string	The identifier of the Smart Contract State to be read.
Output Parameters		Type	Description

	response	JSON	The details of the Smart Contract State with the provided ID is returned in JSON format in the response.
Notes			
Refer to the Deliverable E4.1 for the Data Models of the Smart Contract State that will be returned.			

Table 3-22 GET All SC-States Endpoint

Operation name: GetAllSCStates (/market /scstate)			
Description		Endpoint for reading all Smart Contract States.	
Input Parameters		Type	Description
	N/A	N/A	N/A
Output Parameters		Type	Description
	response	List	Contains all of the Smart Contract State objects in the Trading DLT.
Notes			
Refer to the Deliverable E4.1 for the Data Models of the list of Smart Contract States that will be returned.			

3.5 Workflow Example

This section describes the different workflows for each subcomponent of the DLT system.

3.5.1 Identity Manager API

When a new actor wants to initialize an instance in its infrastructure, an initial procedure takes place to initialize the module of Identity Manager API, this operation is done a single time in the deployment. It consists in performing a process called onboarding, which is the connection to the pool of interconnected Hyperledger Indy nodes, i.e. the decentralized validators and observers of the Identity DLT. This deployment normally is packed and launched via docker compose, connecting to the network of Indy, this network maintains the state of the ledger, verifying its transactions and receiving new ones.

Hyperledger Indy is a public permissioned network, which means that anybody can see the transaction but not everyone can write the transaction into the ledger. One of the roles that allows to write transaction into the Hyperledger Indy ledger is named *steward*. This is due because Indy is designed to be operated such that everyone can see the contents of the blockchain (public), but only pre-approved participants, known as stewards, are permitted to participate in the validation process (permissioned).

During the deployment, a steward user is created to access and write the transactions into the ledger. A seed is given to the Identity Manager API and a steward user is created based on this seed. For this development stage, the same seed is used in every new stakeholder instance deployment, so basically the same steward is used for every new user, meaning that, overall, just one steward user exists to access the Identity DLT.

As an example of the use of functions described in section 3.4.1, when an actor wants to deploy a new instance, creating its own Identity API, it would use the function DeployInstance to do the process of onboarding into the network of Hyperledger Indy. This new instance would have access to the pool of nodes of Hyperledger Indy. This function creates a steward to publish into the Identity DLT, which until the stage of the development of this deliverable, the steward is created using the same seed for every instantiation, meaning that the steward created is equal for every user. Then this actor would use the function CreateNewInstance to assign a new DID for its profile. The Hyperledger Indy framework randomly generates this new DID and a verkey (a private verification key), and to finalize, with the function AddInstacetoledger, this DID is published into the Identity DLT.

After this instantiation, a new DID randomly generated is assigned to the stakeholder and it is stored in the Identity DLT, using the steward for so. Until now, there are no authorization, meaning that for every new deployment, a trustee role is given to the new user, but the differentiation between trustee users and non-trustee users will be added in the upcoming stages of the project. The diagram of Figure 3-3 shows the workflow:

Figure 3-3 Actor deploying instance and receiving an id.

When creating an item (offer/order/SC-state) to be stored in the ledger, the Identity Manager API module is responsible to generate a pseudonym - an anonymous identity for the order or offer. This pseudonym is linked to the DID of the actor which is publishing the item. The ID of the recently created item is returned to the respective API that requested the ID: The offer ID is returned to the Offering API, the order ID to the Order

API, and the SC-state ID to the SC-state API. The three modules send requests to the Identity API, which uses the steward once created in the deployment to publish and manage the IDs in the Identity DLT.

With an instance created and an actor DID published into the Identity DLT, it is possible to verify whether an actor is present in the ledger or not using the function CompareVerkey, which compares the verkey passed as parameter with the one present in the Identity DLT for an specified actor. This function is specially used before generating a DID for an item (offer/order) or for a SC-state, to verify that the actor that is putting them is the correct one. Once the identity is verified, the functions CreateItemDID and CreateSCstateDID generate a DID associated to the item or to the SC-state and links them to the corresponding actor.

As it occurs with the creation of the DID for an actor, which is randomly generated by the Identity API during the instantiation process described in Figure 3-3, it is required a steward to write offer/order/SC-state items into the ledger. So, after the item ID is randomly generated by the Identity API, this module is called again to access the Identity DLT and publish the item ID, which is connected with the publisher actor. Figure 3-4 illustrated this workflow:

Figure 3-4 Orders, offers, and SC-State id creation.

3.5.2 Offering API

Figure 3-5 shows the workflow of how components interact with the Offering API. The workflows of the five provided API endpoints are demonstrated there: GET all offers, GET all offers for a specified cluster ID, POST (create) a new offer, PUT (update) an existing offer and DELETE an offer from the Trading DLT. In most of these scenarios, the Smart Contract State Composer makes the necessary calls to the Offering API. The

exception is when the Smart Discovery application makes a GET request to read all offers for a specified cluster ID. For each operation, a response code from the API indicates the status of the operation, i.e. success or error.

Figure 3-5 Offering API Workflow

GET all offers: This operation returns a list of all the available offers in the Trading DLT, this endpoint could be used when a new order is to be created.

GET offers by cluster ID: This endpoint returns all of the offers that contain the specified cluster ID and is used when offers are being discovered via the Smart Discovery application.

POST a new offer: In this case, a JSON document containing all the data of the offer is sent in the body of the POST request to the API.

PUT an existing offer: To update an existing offer in the Trading DLT, the identifier of the offer needs to be sent as a parameter to the API. A JSON document containing the fields of the offer is also sent to the API in the body of the PUT request.

DELETE an offer: this workflow shows how the API responds to a call to the DELETE endpoint which is used to cancel an existing offer. A record of the offer remains in the Trading DLT, but its status will be updated to 'cancelled' to indicate that the offer is no longer available for purchase.

3.5.3 Order API

Figure 3-6 below shows the workflow of interactions of components with the Order API. This API has four implemented endpoint operations which are displayed below: POST (create) a new order, GET all orders, PUT (update) an existing order and DELETE (cancel) an order from the Trading DLT. For each operation, the API responds with a response code that indicates the success of the operation on the Trading DLT.

POST order: this workflow shows an example of how the Order API is used during the order creation process. The SCSC makes a POST request to the API, sending the data of the order to be recorded in JSON format in the body of the request.

GET all orders: This workflow demonstrates how the API responds to a request to return all the orders in the Trading DLT.

PUT order: To update an existing order in the Trading DLT, the identifier of the order needs to be sent as a parameter to the API. A JSON object containing the fields of the order is also sent to the API in the body of the PUT request.

DELETE order: this workflow shows how the API responds to a call to the DELETE endpoint which is used to cancel an active order. A record of the order remains in the Trading DLT, but the status will be updated to 'cancelled'.

Order API

Figure 3-6 Order API Workflow

3.5.4 SC-State API

Figure 3-7 shows the workflow of interactions of components with the SC-State API. The Smart Contract states can be retrieved by requesting all SC-States or by specifying the id of a SC-State and receiving a specific record.

GET All Smart Contract States: Retrieve a list of all SC-States recorded.

GET Smart Contract State: An individual SC-State can be retrieved by including the identifier of the required SC-State in the request as a parameter. A JSON object is then returned with the data of the required SC-State.

POST Smart Contract State: The Smart Contract State Composer sends a Smart Contract state object to the SC-State API to be stored in the Trading DLT. The SC-State API then writes a deployment message to the “deployment_request” topic in the Data Bus to trigger the deployment of the resources specified in the SC-State.

PUT Smart Contract State: The SCSC can updated existing SC-States in the Trading DLT by sending a PUT request to the SC-State API. This can be used to record changes to the status of SLA compliance in the system. The workflow in Figure 3-7 shows how the Proactive SLA Monitoring component writes an alarm to the Data Bus, which is then read by the Smart Contract State Composer. The SCSC then uses the SC-State API to store the violation in the Trading DLT. When the Proactive SLA Monitoring component detects a potential breach, it writes an alert to the Data Bus which is read by the SCSC, but it is not saved to the Trading DLT.

DELETE Smart Contract State: this workflow shows how the API responds to a call to the DELETE request which is used to cancel an active Smart Contract State. A record of the Smart Contract State remains in the Trading DLT, but the status will be updated to ‘cancelled’.

Figure 3-7 SC-State API Workflow

4 Conclusion

The document provides a design of the DLT system of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, which focuses on supporting multi-party collaboration in dynamic 6G environments through the development of a DLT-anchored Smart Marketplace.

This report covers the efforts related to several activities within P3, related to the study and evaluation of suitable DLT solutions (A3.1) and the design of architectures, interfaces and workflows of the DLT system (A3.2). This information will guide the implementation of the 6GENABLERS Marketplace.

The document begins with the comparison of DLT technology alternatives according to a detailed criteria including quantitative tests and qualitative features. It then describes the associated building blocks in depth according to different implementation and integration aspects to be considered by developers.

The document mainly focuses on the design of the components building the DLT system including the deployment of the Identity Manager API, the Offering API, the Order API, the SC-State API. The building blocks define internal systems and the technologies involved in their implementation, the functions provided and the data formats to provide to/from them, and the workflow designed to establish the preconditions and assigned responsibilities to each component.

Overall, this document serves as a valuable specification of the components to implement to build the DLT system of the 6GENABLERS-DLT project, contributing to the advancement and development of 6G systems.

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